

Redox Reaction of Nitric Oxide and Carbon Monoxide over CuO–V₂O₅ System

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Modern industrialisation and enormous increase of automobiles account high degree of atmospheric pollution. Transportation based on fossil fuel combustion alone is a major source of air pollution, emitting noxious gases like carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, unburned hydrocarbons among other species. The conversion of toxic gases into non-toxic products before discharging in the atmosphere, with suitable catalysts, is highly desired. Some countries have developed catalytic converters consisting of noble metals like platinum and platinum-palladium alloys¹, which are not economical to the developing countries. Therefore, cheaper catalyst which can withstand high temperature and free from poisoning, is needed as substitute of the expensive automotive exhaust platinum catalyst.

Brisi and Molinari² reported the preparation of a variety of copper vanadates having the composition Cu_nV₂O_{5+n} (where, n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) and Fleury^{3,4} confirmed the compositions. Palanna *et al.*^{5,6} reported their electrical and magnetic properties, and thermal studies were made by others^{7,8}. In the present communication, brief studies on simultaneous oxidation-reduction of nitric oxide and carbon monoxide over Cu_nV₂O_{5+n} have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The temperature dependence of NO conversion as function of catalyst temperature for different compositions is shown in Fig. 1. As the copper

Fig 1 Temperature dependence of NO conversion, 3×10^3 GHSV (1) CuV₂O₆, (2) Cu₂V₂O₇, (3) Cu₃V₂O₈, (4) Cu₄V₂O₉ and (5) Cu₅V₂O₁₀

content increases, the activity increases, except in the case of Cu₄V₂O₉ which showed marginally lower activity than Cu₃V₂O₈. Cu₅V₂O₁₀ showed highest activity and CuV₂O₆ the lowest. Table 1 shows the product distribution for the reduction of NO by CO over Cu_nV₂O_{5+n} system. It is evident from Fig. 1 that higher the copper content, higher is the NO conversion. V₂O₅ alone is a poor catalyst for NO-CO reaction, even after activation with H₂ at 673 K for 1h it showed poor catalytic activity. This may be so because V₂O₅ is oxygen-deficient having the formula V₂O_{5-x}, where x = 0.01, so that it is difficult to remove more lattice oxygen because of high binding energy. When CuO

is incorporated in V_2O_5 , the binding energy decreases hence it facilitates donation of oxygen and copper ion acts as good site for NO adsorption¹³.

TABLE 1—PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION FOR THE REDUCTION NO WITH CO OVER $Cu_nV_2O_{5+n}$ SYSTEM*

Catalyst	BET Surface area $m^2 g^{-1}$	NO conversion %	Mole (%)		
			CO ₂	N ₂	N ₂ O
CuV ₂ O ₆	0.52	53	61.8	31.1	7.1
Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇	0.75	59	62.4	30.0	7.6
Cu ₃ V ₂ O ₈	0.54	74	62.5	31.4	6.1
Cu ₄ V ₂ O ₉	0.68	67	62.0	29.4	8.6
Cu ₅ V ₂ O ₁₀	0.80	92	6.43	30.6	5.1

*Inlet composition 5% NO, 5% CO in Ar, pressure, 1 atm; at 683 K catalyst temperature and 3×10^3 GHSV

It is recognised¹⁴ that NO adsorbs more strongly on reduced transition metal oxides than on oxidised samples. It can be adsorbed as nitrosyl with the nitrogen or the oxygen bound to the metal¹⁵. In addition, dissociative adsorption is found on reduced metal oxides, accompanied by oxidation of pre-reduced catalyst by NO + CO reaction, with the formation of CO₂, N₂O and N₂, the following scheme is suggested to account for the observed products :

where V^* is the reduced catalyst site and VO is the oxidised catalyst site. As the temperature of the catalyst increase, higher activity is observed (Fig. 1) but the amount of N₂O in the product decreases and above 740 K only CO₂ and N₂ are the products. This shows that at higher temperature, reaction (2) is favoured.

The possible mechanism of the reduction of NO by CO over different catalysts was proposed by some investigators^{1,12,13,16}. As seen from the observed products, the mechanism appears to be as follows :

where, MO is the oxide catalyst material and M^* the reduced catalyst site. It is considered that the catalytic reduction of NO by CO proceeds according to a redox mechanism, with the reduction of active site being rate-controlling^{12,16}.

Copper vanadates were tested for studying a model NO-CO reaction and no studies were made to observed the life, poisoning and sintering effect of the catalysts. These catalysts did not show very promising activity which might be due to their low surface area.

Experimental

The compounds of compositions CuV₂O₆, Cu₂V₂O₇, Cu₃V₂O₈, Cu₄V₂O₉ and Cu₅V₂O₁₀ were prepared^{2,7,9,10} by taking appropriate molar ratio of CuO and V₂O₅, mixed in an agate mortar using acetone to facilitate intimate mixing. The mixture was palletised and fired in an electric furnace, initially at 800 K for 24 h and then at 925 K for 48 h. However, the thermal treatment of the reacting oxides was varied with the composition of the constituent oxides. The products were characterised by X-ray powder diffraction technique using CuK_α radiation, filtered through nickel. The specific surface area of the sample was determined by the BET nitrogen adsorption method¹¹.

The simultaneous oxidation-reduction of reaction between NO and CO was studies in a conitnuous flow fix-bed quartz reactor, the detailed procedure being reported elsewhere¹². The catalytic activity was determined using feed gas composition of 5% NO, 5% CO and 90% Ar. The feed gases and products were analysed by employing an on-line gas chromatograph with molecular sieve 13X and Porapak Q columns, using hydrogen as carrier gas. Each catalyst (~3 g) was taken

NOTE

in the reactor to study the temperature dependence of NO conversion. Before the reaction, the catalyst was activated at 673 K in hydrogen atmosphere for ~0.5 h, then cooled down to room temperature.

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